

Beyond the Known: Challenging Beal's Conjecture with Fresh Eyes

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Preface

And just as a disclaimer, the try is completely innovative and bold, so please before you start judging please change your lenses ;). Thanks in advance my dears!

Also note: I AM NOT A PROFESSIONAL MATHEMATICIAN AND THAT THIS IS ONLY AMATEUR TEENAGE WORK DONE WITH VERY LITTLE RESSOURCES, anyway sending LOVE!

Abstract

This is in some kind a simple and innocent try to tackle one of the craziest conjectures by a random kid out in this world, only with a pen, papers – a lot –, an old Nokia phone – RIP – for instant research (it had data, don't worry;) and let's not forget the help to grasp some advanced math concepts from a guy in my bus; thank you;). YEAH! Life's easy, anyway, here you go.

Introduction

The Beal Conjecture states that for any natural numbers other than 0,

$$a^x + b^y = c^z,$$

with $a, b, c > 2$, only exists if and only if a, b and c have a common factor other than 1. Note that all numbers here are in \mathbb{N}^* .

Try

Let

$$x = \alpha + 2, \quad y = \beta + 2, \quad z = \gamma + 2$$

with $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in \mathbb{N}^*$.

The expression $a^x + b^y = c^z$ becomes

$$a^{\alpha+2} + b^{\beta+2} = c^{\gamma+2}$$

which is just

$$a^\alpha \cdot a^2 + b^\beta \cdot b^2 = c^\gamma \cdot c^2.$$

And let

$$m = a^\alpha, \quad n = b^\beta, \quad k = c^\gamma,$$

then the expression just becomes

$$m \cdot a^2 + n \cdot b^2 = k \cdot c^2.$$

And we know that original Pythagorean triplets come without a common factor, while all others are just original ones with a certain factor; example: if (a, b, c) is a Pythagorean triplet then (ha, hb, hc) is also a triplet.

Proof by Contradiction

Then if $(m \cdot a^2, n \cdot b^2, k \cdot c^2)$ is an original triplet, in other words:

$$\gcd(m \cdot a^2, n \cdot b^2, k \cdot c^2) = 1,$$

A, B and C should exist in \mathbb{N}^* as

$$m \cdot a^2 = A^2, \quad n \cdot b^2 = B^2, \quad k \cdot c^2 = C^2,$$

from which the statement

$$(a\sqrt{m}, b\sqrt{n}, c\sqrt{k}) \in \mathbb{N}^*$$

should be true.

AND SINCE WE ARE TRYING TO PROVE BEAL'S CONJECTURE AND NOT DIS-PROVE IT THEN WE SHOULD JUST PROVE:

$$a^x + b^y = c^z$$

can't exist in \mathbb{N}^* when x, y and z are all even.

Conclusion

In order to prove or disprove – which is unlikely – Beal's Conjecture you have to prove or disprove my new conjecture that I declare: **Amine's Pythagorean Triplets Conjecture.**

The Amine's Pythagorean Triplets Conjecture states that:

“NO PYTHAGOREAN TRIPLETS THAT ARE ALL PERFECT POWERS THEMSELVES EXIST.”

The proof is left as an exercise for the reader, if you do it contact me in this life or in the afterlife.

END